

Nile Blue as Redox Indicator in Cerimetry*

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The use of Nile Blue, a dye belonging to the oxazine group, as a redox indicator in the cerimetric titration of iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III), uranium(IV), molybdenum(V), vanadium(IV) and hydroquinone has been reported. The titration conditions in sulphuric, hydrochloric, and acetic acid media have been established and the transition potentials of the indicator have also been determined.

THE use of a dye as a redox indicator consists of two aspects: (1) the dye first gets reduced to the leuco form and this leuco form of the dye gets oxidised to the normal form by an oxidant, and (2) the normal form of the dye is oxidised to its oxidised form. Reductants like titanium(III), chromium(II), vanadium(II) etc. reduce the normal form of a dye to the leuco form and hence the use of a dye as a redox indicator in these systems falls under the first aspect. On the other hand, reductants like iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III), etc. cannot reduce the dyes to their leuco forms. Consequently, the functioning of a dye as a redox indicator in such systems comes under the second aspect.

Almost all the dyes which have been reported as redox indicators involve the first aspect, viz., the reduction to the leuco form and subsequent oxidation to the normal form during titration with an oxidant. However, investigations on dyes based on the oxidation of the normal forms to their oxidised forms have not been very exhaustive.

Nile Blue belongs to the oxazine group of dyes. This dye has been used as a pH^1 and acid-base²⁻⁵ indicator and its use as a redox indicator, involving its reduction to the leuco form and subsequent oxidation of the leuco form to the normal form was reported by Letort⁶, who used it in titrations of titanium(III). The use of Nile Blue as a redox indicator, based on the oxidation of the normal form of the dye to the oxidised form, has not been reported till now. We have been able to achieve this and the results obtained in the studies on the use of this indicator in the cerimetric titration of iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), arsenic(III), uranium(IV), vanadium(IV), molybdenum(V) and hydroquinone are presented in this paper. In this connection, it may be pointed out that Venkateswara Rao, Radhakrishna Murty and Kamala Sastry⁷ have

recently reported the use of two other oxazine dyes, Brilliant Cresyl Blue and Gallocyanine as redox indicators in cerimetry. They report that the normal forms of these two dyes are oxidised to their corresponding oxidised forms.

Experimental

Reagents. All the reagents used were of reagent grade quality. 0.1 N solutions of cerium(IV) sulphate, iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), uranium(IV), vanadium(IV), molybdenum(V) and hydroquinone were prepared and standardised. 0.1 N solution of arsenic(III) was prepared from Merck 'pro analysi' arsenious oxide.

Indicator solutions. The following four samples of the dye, Nile Blue, were used in the present investigation.

Name of the sample	Manufacturer	Colour Index No. as mentioned by the manufacturer
Nile Blue	Gurr	51180 (In the catalogue)
Nile Blue Sulphate	Chroma	51180 (In the catalogue)
Bile Blue Chloride	Tokyo Kasei Kogyo Co., Japan.	51180 (On the bottle)
Nile Blue Chlorohydrate.	G. Grubler	---

0.1% solutions of the above samples were prepared in doubly distilled water. We have observed that the indicator action of the solutions is retained for about 5-6 months and that 0.15 ml (3 drops) of the dye solution is required to impart perceptible colour changes at the end points in a total volume of 50 ml. If the volume of the titration mixture exceeds 50 ml, suitable higher volumes of the indicator should be used.

General Procedure

We recommend the following general procedure for the titrations.

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Treat an aliquot of the reductant solution with enough 1 : 1 sulphuric, hydrochloric or acetic acid so as to maintain the necessary overall acid concentration and dilute to 50 ml. Add 0.15 ml of 0.1% Nile Blue solution and titrate with 0.1 N cerium(IV) sulphate solution. The titration conditions and colour changes at the end points are given in Table 1 and the results are incorporated in Table 2.

precipitate does not affect either the titre value or the detection and the end point.

Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II) interfere in the titrations in the three acid media. Up to 26 mg of Cr(III) does not interfere in the titration in hydrochloric and acetic acid media but interferes in sulphuric acid medium.

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF TITRATION AND COLOUR CHANGES AT THE END POINTS

Reductant	Medium	Colour change at the end point	
Iron(II)	(1) 0.5–3.0N H ₂ SO ₄	Bright green to pink	
	(2) 0.1–1.0N HCl	Green to pink	
	(3) 1.0–6.0N CH ₃ COOH	Green to pink	
Hexacyanoferrate(II)*	(1) 0.5–3.0N H ₂ SO ₄	Green to yellowish orange	
	(2) 0.1–1.0N HCl	Green to pink	
	(3) 0.5–3.0N CH ₃ COOH	Green to pink	
Arsenic(III)	(a) OsO ₄ (3 drops of 0.1%) as catalyst		
	(1) 0.5–3.0N H ₂ SO ₄	Green to pink	
	(2) 0.5–6.0N CH ₃ COOH	Green to pink	
	(b) ICI (0.017M) as catalyst		
	(1) 0.5–3.0N H ₂ SO ₄ + 3 drops of ICI	Green to pink	
	(2) 2.5–4.0N HCl + 1.0 ml of ICI	Light yellow to pink	
	(3) 1.5–6.0 N CH ₃ COOH + 0.5 ml of ICI	Green to pink	
	(c) Ferron (0.5 ml of 0.005M) as catalyst		
	0.5–3.0N H ₂ SO ₄	Green to pink	
	0.1–1.0N HCl	Green to pink	
Uranium(IV)	0.1–1.0N HCl	Green to pink	
	Vanadium(IV)	(1) 0.5–2.5N H ₂ SO ₄	Green to pink
		(2) 0.3–1.0N HCl	Green to pink
(3) 1.0–6.0N CH ₃ COOH		Green to pink	
Molybdenum(V)	(1) 1.0–4.0N H ₂ SO ₄	Green to pink	
	(2) 1.0–3.0N HCl	Green to pink	
Hydroquinone	(1) 0.5–3.0N H ₂ SO ₄	Green to yellowish brown @	
	(2) 0.1–1.0N HCl	Green to pink	
	(3) 1.0–6.0N CH ₃ COOH	Green to pink	

* Total volume of titration mixture : 100 ml.
@ Green to pink in 0.01N solutions.

Titration of iron(II). Phosphoric acid does not interfere when the titration is performed in 1.5–3.0 N sulphuric acid medium only; it interferes in media of sulphuric acid concentrations less than 1.5 N as well as hydrochloric acid (0.1–1.0 N) and acetic acid (1.0–6.0 N).

The following amounts of coloured ions do not interfere in the titration : Co(II) : 85 mg, Ni(II) : 70 mg, Cu(II) : 90 mg and Cr(III) : 50 mg.

Titration of hexacyanoferrate(II). In titrations in acetic acid media, a white precipitate will be formed during the initial stages of the titration and dissolves during the final stages of the titration. The

Titration of arsenic(III) :

(a) *OsO₄ as catalyst.* Phosphoric acid does not interfere in media of 2 N and above sulphuric acid, but interferes in acetic acid medium.

(b) *ICI as catalyst.* While titrating in hydrochloric acid medium, the indicator should be added near the end point (the indicator will be completely bleached if added in the beginning) and waiting for about 30 sec is necessary near the end point. Titrations in acetic acid medium yield satisfactory results only when the order of addition of solutions is : acid, iodine monochloride, water and arsenic(III). If this order is not followed, lower titres will be obtained.

TABLE 2—CERIMETRIC TITRATION OF IRON(II), HEXACYANOFERRATE(II), ARSENIC(III), URANIUM(IV), VANADIUM(IV), MOLYBDENUM(V) AND HYDROQUINONE WITH CERIUM(IV) SULPHATE

Reductant	Amount, mg	
	Taken	Found
Iron(II)	4.42	4.42
	79.66	79.75
Hexacyanoferrate(II)	13.78	13.74
	233.20	234.00
Arsenic(III)	7.40	7.38
	100.40	100.20
Uranium(IV)	7.37	7.36
	46.52	46.55
Vanadium(IV)	2.20	2.20
	52.53	52.66
Molybdenum(V)	1.39	1.39
	24.60	24.58
Hydroquinone	6.89	6.89
	122.20	122.10

(c) *Ferron as catalyst.* When this titration is carried out in acetic acid medium, a green precipitate is formed and the detection of the end point becomes difficult. Rao, Subrahmanyam and Rao⁸ have reported that titrations in hydrochloric acid medium give erroneous results and hence the titrations in hydrochloric acid medium were not attempted.

The amounts of coloured ions that are tolerable in the cerimetric titration of arsenic(III) using OsO_4 as catalyst are: Ni(II): 28 mg, Cu(II): 12 mg, Cr(III): 20 mg, and Co(II): 30 mg (in acetic acid medium Co interferes even at low concentrations).

Titration of uranium(IV). The pink colour obtained at the end point becomes green in about 1 min and the end point should be taken as that at which the pink colour is stable for at least 1 min.

In sulphuric and acetic acid media, although the end points could be observed, the results obtained are erratic and addition of phosphoric acid does not improve the situation.

Titration of vanadium(IV). In sulphuric and hydrochloric acid media, the indicator should be added towards the close of the titration, whereas in acetic acid medium, it can be added even at the beginning. Moreover, in sulphuric and hydrochloric acid media, waiting for about 15–20 sec is necessary during the final stages of the titration and in titrations in acetic acid medium, waiting for about 5–10 sec is essential near the end point.

Phosphoric acid interferes in this titration in sulphuric and hydrochloric acid media by giving higher titres. In acetic acid medium, a precipitate will be formed in presence of phosphoric acid and consequently, the titration becomes unsatisfactory.

The titration is not affected by the presence of 2.5 mg of Cr(III), 30 mg of Co(II), 30 mg of Ni(II) and 32 mg of Cu(II).

Titration of molybdenum(V). The detection of the end point becomes difficult if the amount of molybdenum(V) exceeds 1.4 mmoles.

The presence of phosphoric acid is not necessary and even if present, it does not interfere.

Titration of hydroquinone. Phosphoric acid interferes in this titration in hydrochloric and acetic acid media and in media of 0.5–1.5 N sulphuric acid, but not at higher sulphuric acid concentrations.

The titration is not vitiated by the presence of 75 mg of Cr(III), 115 mg of Co(II), 55 mg of Ni(II) and 60 mg of Cu(II).

Indicator corrections. In titrations of 0.1 N solutions of the reductants with 0.1 N cerium(IV) solutions, no indicator correction is necessary. However, an indicator correction of 0.15 ml of 0.01 N has to be applied for 0.15 ml of 0.1% Nile Blue while performing titrations with 0.01 N cerium(IV) solutions.

Titrations in 0.01 N solutions. Titrations of 0.01 N solutions of the reductants with 0.01 N cerium(IV) sulphate solution using Nile Blue as indicator also yield good results, provided an indicator correction of 0.15 ml is applied. 0.01 N and 0.025 N solutions of arsenic(III) cannot be accurately titrated with cerium(IV) sulphate of corresponding concentrations using iodine monochloride and ferron as catalysts. However, the titrations can be performed accurately in sulphuric acid medium and using osmic acid as catalyst.

Transition potentials. The transition potentials (vs N.H.E.) of Nile Blue for the iron(II)-cerium(IV) titration in the three acid media are as follows:

- (a) 1.0 N sulphuric acid medium : $1050 \pm 10 \text{ mV}$
 (b) 0.5 N hydrochloric acid medium : $1100 \pm 10 \text{ mV}$
 (c) 3.0 N acetic acid medium : $980 \pm 10 \text{ mV}$

The four different samples of Nile Blue employed in this investigation have the same value for the transition potential.

Reverse titrations. The indicator, Nile Blue gets destroyed by irreversible oxidation, in presence of excess of cerium(IV) sulphate and hence the reverse titrations are not feasible.

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